

STUDIES ON ENZYME LIPASE. COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LIPASES FROM OIL SEED CAKES

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Lipases are obtained from different oil seed cakes like ghani cake, propeller cake and pressed cake and it is found that generally in all cases, the activity is low but out of the three, the activity decreases in the order: pressed, ghani and propeller cake lipase. Ghani cake lipase being cheaper and moderately active has been used for further experiments.

With respect to the effect of the nature of the buffer, substrate and the lipase it is found that the optimum pH is generally on the acidic side and the change in the optimum pH is not much with the nature of the buffer but is slight with the nature of the substrate. The castor and groundnut samples are the best active, groundnut oil is the best substrate and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer is the best buffer.

Optimum buffer concentration and optimum substrate concentration depend upon the nature of the lipase and the percentage hydrolysis of the oil goes on increasing with the enzyme concentration. The optimum temperature for the enzymic hydrolysis of the oil by cake lipase is 37° – 40° .

Generally organic salts like glycine, ascorbic acid, etc. accelerate the lipase activity to a greater extent and $MnSO_4$ and ammonium phosphate from inorganic salts also possess greater accelerating power.

The activity of petroleum ether-dried sample slowly decreases on ageing. The acetone-drained sample keeps its activity fairly constant even though it is low.

Ramakrishnan and Nevgi (M.Sc. Thesis, Bombay University, 1947) have carried out a general study on the lipases obtained from different oil seeds. In the present work an attempt has been made to investigate oil seed cakes to obtain cheaper and active variety of lipase from them. An experiment was conducted with the following oil seed cakes to study their lipolytic activity: (1) Castor cake (*Ricinus communis*), (2) Groundnut cake (*Arachis hypogea*); (3) Sesame cake (*Sesamum indicum*); (4) Mysore seed cake (*Guizotia abyssinica*), (5) Mustard cake (*Brassica nigra*), (6) Safflower cake (*carthamus*) and (7) Cottonseed cake (*Gossypium herbiceum*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Nature of the Oil Cake.—The first factor to be considered is the type of the oil cake to be chosen for the experiment. There are three types of oil cakes available—oil cake from cold drawn press method, oil cake from *ghani* method and oil cake from propeller method. These three oil cakes were taken and lipases prepared from them according to Longnecker and Haly's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2019) and tested for their activities. The hydrolysis of groundnut oil by these lipases was studied.

Each experiment consisted of groundnut oil (1 c.c.), water (5 c.c.) and cake lipase (0.1 g.) in a test tube and kept in the incubator for 24 hours at 37° . Then the contents were removed and titrated against $N/10$ sodium hydroxide after the addition of neutral alcohol (25 c.c.) and warming for sometime. Always a blank accompanied the sample. Necessary precautions were taken to take readings under sterile conditions. The difference between the sample and the blank gives the activity of the lipase in terms of c.c. of $N/10$ sodium hydroxide. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Oil cake : Groundnut oil.

Set No.	Source of lipase.	Diff. bet the sample & the blank in terms of c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH for					
		Castor.	Groundnut.	Seasame.	Mysore seed.	Safflower.	Mustard seed cake.
1	Cold pressed cake	0.5	0.4	0.8	0.5	0.9	0.6
2	Ghani cake	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.3	0.6	0.4
3	Propeller cake	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.7

It appears from Table I that the activity is most in cold pressed cake lipase, least in propeller cake, and moderate in ghani cake. Out of the three, ghani cake is the most suitable since its changes are moderate and it is available in plenty if the new method of extracting oil suggested by Banerjee and Ramanamurti (*Ind. J. Med Res.*, 1948, 36, 4) is developed in the country. Hence, for further experiments ghani cake was chosen.

Different Factors controlling the Activity of Cake Lipase

It has been observed that the cake lipases are not very reactive. These cannot be used for fat splitting on an industrial scale unless they show appreciable activity. Hence different factors like H-ion concentration, nature of the buffer, substrate and lipase, effect of buffer, substrate and enzyme concentrations, effect of salts, temperature, etc. on the activity of the cake lipase are to be studied in order to find out the optimum conditions for their maximum activity.

The ghani cakes of different oil seeds were powdered well and packed in a filter paper and Soxhleted with low boiling petroleum ether for about 3 hours till the oil was completely removed. The packet was taken out, the extracted mass spread over a long sheet of filter paper, dried completely free from petroleum ether at room temperature, sieved through a 60 mesh sieve and the fine powder so obtained was preserved in a bottle after adding a few drops of toluene to prevent bacterial growth and used for further experiments.

Effect of the Nature of the Buffer, Substrate and Lipase on the Activity of Cake Lipase.—Disodium Phosphate-citric acid buffer mixtures of different p_H were prepared according to McIlvaine's method (*Biochem. J.*, 1929, 40, 183), sodium acetate—hydrochloric acid and sodium acetate—acetic acid buffer mixtures of different p_H were prepared according to Walpole's method (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1914, 106, 2501). The buffer mixtures were tested for their respective p_H and, if necessary, adjusted by addition of any of the constituents of the buffer mixtures. The above buffer mixtures were used in the following experiments.

The hydrolysis of different freshly prepared oils were carried out using the three buffers and different cake lipases.

Each set of the experiments consisted of the oil (1 c.c.), water (5 c.c.), cake lipase (0.1 g.) and 2 c.c. of buffer mixtures of varying p_H value and a few drops of toluene in a test tube, corked well, and incubated for 24 hours at 37°. Always a blank accom-

panied each sample. After the period of incubation, each test tube was taken out and the contents titrated against $N/10$ sodium hydroxide after adding 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol and warming for sometime. Necessary precautions were taken to take the readings under sterile conditions. The difference between the sample and the blank gives the activity of the lipase in terms of c.c. of $N/10$ sodium hydroxide. The results are shown in Tables III and IV.

The combined results for the hydrolysis of the different oils by different cake lipases using disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer with special reference to the optimum p_n are shown in Table III.

TABLE II

Buffer : Disodium phosphate-citric acid.

Difference in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample and the blank in case of

Set No.	p_n .	Castor.	Ground-nut.	Seasame.	Mysore.	Safflower.	Mustard.	Cotton seed.
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Groundnut oil = 1 c.c. F.F.A. = 0.05 c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH for 1 c.c. of oil. Sap. value = 188. I.V. = 100.1.

1	2.8	2.8	3.2	2.7	2.5	2.6	3.7	2.5
2	3.2	3.2	3.7	3.0	2.6	2.9	4.1	2.7
3	3.6	3.9	4.0	3.2	3.0	3.1	5.0	3.0
4	3.8	5.2	4.4	4.4	3.3	3.5	4.2	3.2
5	4.4	3.8	5.3	3.0	3.8	3.9	3.9	3.0
6	4.8	3.2	4.9	2.8	4.6	4.2	3.6	2.7
7	5.2	3.0	4.5	2.4	4.8	4.5	3.1	2.3
8	5.9	2.7	4.1	2.1	4.0	4.1	2.7	2.1
9	6.2	2.5	3.8	1.8	3.7	3.8	2.4	1.8
10	7.2	2.1	3.5	1.5	3.2	3.2	2.1	1.5

Seasame oil = 1 c.c. F.F.A. = 0.05 c.c. Sap. value = 189.3. I.V. = 114.2.

1	2.8	4.0	4.1	4.3	3.1	2.2	3.9	2.7
2	3.2	4.2	4.3	4.5	3.3	2.6	4.2	2.9
3	3.6	4.5	4.6	4.9	3.7	2.9	4.5	3.1
4	3.8	5.0	4.8	4.6	4.0	3.2	4.8	2.8
5	4.4	4.6	5.1	4.3	4.3	3.6	4.3	2.5
6	4.8	4.2	4.4	4.0	3.9	3.8	4.0	2.3
7	5.2	4.0	4.0	3.7	3.6	3.8	4.0	2.3
8	5.9	3.8	3.6	3.3	3.4	3.9	3.4	1.8
9	6.2	2.5	3.8	3.0	3.1	3.5	3.1	1.5
10	7.2	3.1	3.0	2.7	2.9	3.2	2.8	1.2

TABLE II (contd.)

Difference in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample & the blank in case ofSet. No. ρ_H . Castor G. nut. Sesame. Mysore. Safflower. Mustard. Cottonseed.

Castor oil = 1 c.c. F.F.A. = 0.30 c.c. Sap. value = 176.7. IV = 83.7.

1	2.8	5.5	3.6	1.9	1.3	1.5	1.9	2.1
2	3.2	5.8	1.9	2.1	1.6	1.8	2.2	2.4
3	3.6	6.1	3.1	2.5	1.9	2.1	2.5	2.7
4	3.8	5.7	3.4	2.8	2.1	2.5	2.9	2.3
5	4.4	5.3	3.8	3.1	2.4	2.7	2.6	2.0
6	4.8	5.0	3.5	2.9	2.8	3.0	2.3	1.8
7	5.2	4.7	3.2	2.6	2.1	3.2	2.1	1.5
8	5.9	4.2	3.0	2.3	1.8	2.9	1.9	1.3
9	6.2	3.9	2.7	2.0	1.5	2.6	1.6	1.0
10	7.2	3.6	2.3	1.0	1.2	2.4	1.2	0.7

Mysore seed oil = 1 c.c. F.F.A. = 0.05 c.c. Sap. value = 185.6. I.V. = 118.6.

1	2.8	3.9	2.5	3.3	3.0	3.0	3.6	1.4
2	3.2	4.2	2.8	3.5	3.3	2.6	4.0	1.8
3	3.6	4.7	3.0	3.8	3.7	2.9	4.3	2.1
4	3.8	4.5	3.1	4.1	4.2	3.2	3.9	2.9
5	4.4	4.4	3.2	3.9	4.6	3.6	3.7	2.6
6	4.8	4.1	5.5	3.6	5.0	3.8	3.4	2.3
7	5.2	3.8	3.1	3.2	4.7	4.1	3.1	2.0
8	5.9	3.5	2.9	3.0	4.3	3.9	2.7	1.7
9	6.2	3.0	2.7	2.8	4.0	3.6	2.4	1.4
10	7.2	2.7	2.2	2.4	3.8	3.2	2.0	1.1

Safflower oil = 1 c.c. F.F.A. = 0.03 c.c. Sap. value = 187.2. I.V. = 143.4.

1	2.8	3.1	3.7	2.9	2.8	3.2	3.1	1.8
2	3.2	3.7	4.1	3.2	3.1	3.4	3.3	2.2
3	3.6	4.0	4.5	3.7	3.5	3.7	3.6	2.7
4	3.8	4.3	4.8	3.4	3.8	4.1	4.0	2.4
5	4.4	4.1	5.1	3.1	4.0	4.4	3.8	2.0
6	4.8	3.8	4.6	2.8	4.3	4.9	3.5	1.8
7	5.2	3.5	4.2	2.5	4.8	5.2	3.2	1.5
8	5.9	3.1	3.8	2.3	4.4	4.7	3.0	1.1
9	6.2	2.7	3.2	2.0	4.0	4.2	2.7	0.8
10	7.2	2.3	3.0	1.7	3.6	3.8	2.3	0.5

TABLE II (contd.)

Difference in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample and the blank in case of

Set No.	p _H .	Castor.	G. nut.	Seasame.	Mysore.	Safflower.	Mustard.	Cottonseed.
Mustard oil = 1 c.c. F.F.A. = 01.0 c.c. Sap. value = 174.4. I. V. = 106.8.								
1	2.8	3.5	3.2	2.3	3.3	2.3	4.3	1.5
2	3.2	3.8	3.4	2.5	3.5	2.7	4.8	1.7
3	3.6	4.1	3.7	2.9	3.7	3.0	5.2	2.0
4	3.8	3.9	4.0	3.2	4.0	3.5	6.4	2.3
5	4.4	3.7	4.2	3.0	4.2	3.9	5.9	2.1
6	4.8	3.4	4.7	2.7	4.5	3.4	5.4	1.8
7	5.2	3.1	4.3	2.5	4.1	3.1	5.1	1.3
8	5.9	2.8	4.1	2.2	3.8	2.7	4.8	1.0
9	6.2	2.5	3.8	1.9	3.5	2.3	4.5	0.7
10	7.2	2.2	3.3	1.6	3.2	2.0	4.2	0.4
Cottonseed oil = 1 c.c. F.F.A. = 0.10 c.c. Sap. value = 154.5 I. V. = 113.2.								
1	2.8	2.1	1.9	2.1	1.3	0.9	1.5	2.5
2	3.2	2.5	2.3	2.4	1.5	1.2	1.8	2.9
3	3.6	3.0	2.7	2.6	1.6	1.5	2.1	3.2
4	3.8	3.3	3.0	2.9	1.9	1.8	2.4	3.5
5	4.4	3.1	3.2	2.7	2.1	2.1	2.2	3.1
6	4.8	2.8	2.9	2.4	2.5	2.5	2.0	2.8
7	5.2	2.6	2.6	2.1	2.3	2.9	1.8	2.5
8	5.9	2.4	2.4	1.8	2.0	2.3	1.5	2.3
9	6.2	2.1	2.1	1.5	1.7	2.0	1.2	2.0
10	7.2	0.9	1.9	1.3	1.3	1.7	0.9	1.7

TABLE III

Buffer : Sodium acetate-HCl.

Groundnut oil = 1 c.c. F.F.A. = 0.05 c.c. Sap. value = 188.6. I. V. = 100.1.

Difference in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample and the blank in case of

Set. No.	p _H .	Castor.	G. nut.	Seasame.	Mysore.	Safflower.	Mustard.	Cottonseed.
1	2.7	3.2	4.8	4.2	3.6	2.4	3.9	2.7
2	3.3	4.3	5.2	4.9	3.2	2.9	4.2	3.1
3	3.9	6.3	5.8	4.6	3.8	3.2	5.3	3.6
4	4.4	5.8	6.1	4.1	4.3	3.4	5.1	3.2
5	4.8	4.9	5.9	3.8	5.2	4.2	7.8	2.9
6	5.2	4.2	5.2	3.3	4.9	5.2	4.5	2.6
7	5.6	3.9	4.8	3.0	4.2	4.8	4.3	2.4
8	6.2	3.6	4.5	2.6	3.1	4.3	4.0	2.1

TABLE IV

Buffer: Sodium acetate-acetic acid.

Groundnut oil = 1 c.c.

Difference in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample and the blank in case of

Set. No.	p_H .	Castor.	G. nut.	Seasame.	Mysore.	Safflower.	Mustard.	Cottonseed
1	2.7	4.8	6.3	4.2	5.1	3.1	4.0	2.9
2	3.3	6.9	6.8	4.9	5.4	3.9	4.3	3.3
3	3.9	8.3	7.2	5.2	5.8	4.3	5.8	3.8
4	4.4	7.5	7.8	4.8	6.1	4.7	5.2	3.5
5	4.8	7.1	7.5	4.2	5.7	5.2	4.8	3.1
6	5.2	6.7	7.1	3.9	5.2	5.6	4.3	3.0
7	5.6	6.4	6.7	3.3	4.0	5.1	4.0	2.8
8	6.2	5.9	6.2	3.0	4.6	4.7	3.7	2.2

TABLE V

Lipase from		Castor oil.		Groundnut oil.		Seasame oil.		Mysore seed oil.		Safflower oil.		Mustard oil.		Cottonseed oil.	
		Opt. p_H .	Max. activity in c.c.	Opt. p_H .	Max. activity in c.c.	Opt. p_H .	Max. activity in c.c.	Opt. p_H .	Max. activity in c.c.	Opt. p_H .	Max. activity in c.c.	Opt. p_H .	Max. activity in c.c.	Opt. p_H .	Max. activity in c.c.
1	Castor	3.6	6.1	3.8	5.2	3.8	5.0	3.6	4.7	3.8	4.3	3.6	4.1	3.8	3.1
2	Groundnut	4.4	3.8	4.4	5.3	4.4	5.1	4.8	5.5	4.4	5.1	4.8	4.7	4.4	3.2
3	Seasame	4.4	3.1	3.8	4.4	3.6	4.9	3.8	4.1	3.6	3.7	3.8	3.2	3.8	2.9
4	Mysore seed	4.8	2.8	4.8	4.6	4.4	4.3	4.8	5.0	5.2	4.8	4.8	4.5	4.8	2.5
5	Safflower	5.2	3.2	5.2	4.5	5.2	4.2	5.2	4.1	5.2	5.2	4.4	3.9	5.2	2.9
6	Mustard	3.8	2.9	3.6	5.0	3.8	4.8	3.6	4.3	3.8	4.0	3.8	6.4	3.8	2.4
7	Cottonseed	3.6	2.7	3.8	3.2	3.6	3.1	3.8	2.9	3.6	2.7	3.8	2.3	3.8	3.5

TABLE VI

Hydrolysis of groundnut oil by different lipases using different buffers.

Set No.	Lipase.	Disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer.		Sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer.		Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer.	
		Opt. p_H .	Max. activity	Opt. p_H .	Max. activity.	Opt. p_H .	Max. activity.
1	Castor	3.8	5.2 c.c.	3.9	6.3 c.c.	3.9	8.9 c.c.
2	Groundnut	4.4	5.3	4.4	6.1	4.4	7.8
3	Seasame	3.8	4.4	3.3	4.9	3.9	5.2
4	Mysore seed	4.8	4.6	4.8	5.2	4.4	6.1
5	Mustard	3.6	5.0	3.0	5.3	3.9	5.8
6	Safflower	5.2	4.5	5.2	5.4	5.2	5.6
7	Cottonseed	3.8	3.2	3.9	3.6	3.9	3.8

From the above tables, it can be seen that the groundnut and castor cake lipases are the best active lipases and groundnut oil is the best substrate in which all the lipases show appreciable activity.

In Table VI, the combined results for the optimum p_H and the maximum activity at the optimum p_H in case of different lipases using different buffers are given. The activity of the lipase appears to go on changing with the nature of the buffer, increasing in the order: disodium phosphate-citric acid, sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. The optimum p_H also varies with the nature of the lipase as well as the nature of the substrates, but the change in the optimum p_H in case of different substrates is small. In all the cases, the optimum p_H is in the acidic side which is a notable feature. The optimum p_H is almost constant and in only a very few cases changes with the nature of the buffer.

So it can be concluded that with the cake lipases, the optimum p_H changes with the nature of the lipase, slightly with the nature of the substrate and almost constant with different buffers. Castor and groundnut cake lipases are the best active lipases, groundnut oil is the best substrate and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer is the best buffer.

Effect of Buffer Concentration on the Hydrolysis of Groundnut Oil by Cake Lipases

As the castor and groundnut cake lipases were found the most active, these two were only used for the rest of the work.

The hydrolysis of groundnut oil by different cake lipases was carried out by changing the concentration of the buffer mixture and keeping the other factors constant; sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of 4.4 p_H was used. The amount of the buffer added varied from 1 to 8 c.c. Each set of the experiments consisted of groundnut oil (1 c.c.), water (5 c.c.), cake lipase (0.1 g.) and varying quantities of acetate buffer and incubated for 24 hours at 37°. Always the blank experiment was carried out. After the period of incubation, the contents of each flask were titrated against $N/10$ sodium hydroxide similarly under conditions as stated earlier. The results are given in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Set No.	Oil.	Buffer added.	Diff. bet. the sample & the blank in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH in case of lipase from	
			Castor.	Groundnut.
1	1.0 c.c.	1.0 c.c.	6.9	7.2
2	"	2.0	7.5	7.8
3	"	3.0	7.8	8.1
4	"	4.0	7.0	7.3
5	"	5.0	6.7	6.2
6	"	6.0	6.3	5.9
7	"	7.0	6.2	4.8
8	"	8.0	5.8	3.9

From the above table buffer concentration appears to play an important role in the enzymic hydrolysis of oil. The optimum buffer concentration is 3 c.c.

Effect of Substrate Concentration on the Hydrolysis of Groundnut Oil by different Cake Lipases

The hydrolysis of groundnut oil was carried out using different lipases by changing the concentration of the oil and keeping the other factors constant using the materials in the same proportions as in earlier experiments.

Acetate buffer of p_H 4.4 (2 c.c.) was used and incubated for 24 hours at 37° . The contents were then titrated against $N/10$ sodium hydroxide following the same procedure as described previously. The results are shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII

Set No.	Oil.	Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in c.c. of $N/10$ NaOH in lipase from		Set No.	Oil.	Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in c.c. of $N/10$ NaOH in lipase from	
		Castor.	Groundnut.			Castor.	Groundnut.
1	1.0 c.c.	7.5	7.8	5	5.0	7.2	5.4
2	2.0	8.3	6.3	6	6.0	7.0	5.1
3	3.0	7.9	6.0	7	7.0	6.7	4.8
4	4.0	7.5	5.8	8	8.0	6.3	4.3

From the above table it can be seen that in general the maximum hydrolysis is obtained when substrate concentration is 1 to 2 c.c. depending on the nature of the lipase and it is very difficult if the concentration is more. Therefore the optimum substrate concentration is 1 to 2 c.c. depending upon the nature of the lipase.

Effect of Enzyme Concentration on the Hydrolysis of Groundnut Oil by different Cake Lipases

Eight sets of experiments were carried out keeping all other factors constant excepting the concentration of the lipase. The materials were in the same amount as used in the previous sets of experiments with varying quantities of enzyme lipase and incubated at 37° for 24 hours. After the period of incubation, the contents were titrated against $N/10$ sodium hydroxide under conditions similar to previous sets of experiments. The results are given in Table IX.

TABLE IX

Set No.	Oil.	Enzyme.	Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in c.c. of $N/10$ NaOH in lipase from		Set No.	Oil.	Enzyme.	Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in c.c. of $N/10$ NaOH in lipase from	
			Castor.	Groundnut.				Castor.	Groundnut.
1	1.0 c.c.	0.1 g.	7.5	7.8	5	1.0 c.c.	0.5 g.	8.7	8.6
2	"	0.2	7.8	8.0	6	"	0.6	9.0	8.9
3	"	0.3	8.1	8.2	7	"	0.7	9.3	9.1
4	"	0.4	8.5	8.4	8	"	0.8	9.5	9.3

The percentage hydrolysis of the oil from Table IX appears to go on increasing as the concentration of the enzyme increases. Hence, greater the concentration of the enzyme, greater is its activity.

Effect of Temperature on Enzymic Hydrolysis of Groundnut Oil by different Cake Lipases

Different sets of experiments were carried out by keeping the contents in the incubator at different temperatures for a fixed time and then titrating the contents against $N/10$ sodium hydroxide. Hydrolysis of groundnut oil was carried out by keeping the contents for two hours at temperatures 28° , 30° , 35° , 40° , 75° and 100° . Experiments were conducted using the materials in the same amounts and under conditions similar to previous experiments and same procedure was followed in titrations against $N/10$ -NaOH. The results are given in Table X.

TABLE X

Set No.	Temp.	Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH in		Set No.	Temp.	Diff. bet. the sample and the blank in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH in	
		Castor lipase.	Groundnut lipase.			Castor lipase.	Groundnut lipase.
1	28.0°	2.7	2.5	5	40.0°	3.6	3.8
2	30.0°	3.2	3.0	6	75.0°	2.0	2.9
3	35.0°	3.5	3.3	7	100.0°	0.0	0.0
4	37.0°	3.7	3.6				

From Table X, it can be seen that the temperature also plays an important role in enzymic hydrolysis of the oils and that the optimum temperature for maximum hydrolysis is 37° to 40° depending on the nature of lipase.

Effect of Salts on Enzymic Hydrolysis of Groundnut Oil by different Cake Lipases

The cake lipases are poor in activity even though they are cheap. If they are to be utilised with advantage, they should be accelerated by using cheap accelerators. Hence the action of the following substances was studied on the hydrolysis of groundnut oil by the cake lipases with a view to ascertaining how far they accelerate the activity of the cake lipases: Strychnine sulphate, albumin, ascorbic acid, sodium taurocholate, sodium acetate, strychnine chloride, glycine, citric acid, gum arabic, acetic acid, ammonium phosphate, sodium phosphate, potassium phosphate, hydrochloric acid, calcium chloride, sodium chloride and manganese sulphate.

Each set of the experiments consisted of 1 c.c. of groundnut oil, 5 c.c. of water, 2 c.c. of acetate buffer of pH 4.4, 0.1 g. of cake lipase and 0.1 g. of salt (or 1 c.c. of $N/10$ salt solution in case of hydrochloric acid and acetic acid), and incubated at 37° for 24 hours. Subsequent procedure followed was the same as in previous experiments. The difference between the sample and the blank in terms of c.c. of $N/10$ sodium hydroxide will give the activity of the lipase.

The difference shows whether a particular substance is an accelerator or inhibitor depending upon whether the difference is a positive one (showing the accelerating effect) or a negative one (showing the inhibiting or retarding effect). The results are given in Table XI.

TABLE XI

Set No.	Name of the salt.	Diff. in c.c. of N/10-NaOH bet. the sample & the blank in		Set No.	Name of the salt.	Diff. in c.c. of N/10-NaOH bet. the sample & the blank in	
		Castor lipase.	Groundnut lipase.			Castor lipase.	Groundnut lipase.
1	Strychnine sulphate	+0.2	-0.3	10	Gum arabic	+1.3	+0.5
2	„ chloride	+0.2	-1.2	11	(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	+2.8	+1.0
3	Albumin	-0.3	-0.5	12	Na ₂ HPO ₄	+1.8	+0.0
4	Sodium taurocholate	+0.5	+0.7	13	KH ₂ PO ₄	+0.8	+0.3
5	Ascorbic acid	+1.0	+0.5	14	MnSO ₄	+0.9	+1.2
6	Sodium acetate	+0.2	+0.0	15	NaCl	+0.2	+0.4
7	Citric acid	+0.1	+0.1	16	HCl	+0.8	+1.1
8	Acetic acid	+0.8	+0.4	17	CaCl ₂	+0.5	+0.3
9	Glycine	+2.8	+1.8				

From the above table it appears that in general ascorbic acid, gum arabic, glycine, etc. accelerate the lipase action. In case of inorganic salts, ammonium phosphate, MnSO₄ and HCl are good accelerators. The organic salts accelerate more which may be due to their way of possessing N₂ in them. Gum arabic and ascorbic acid accelerate perhaps due to their emulsifying action.

It can be seen that the salts which are used for preparing buffer solutions do not hinder the activity of the cake lipases.

Finally it is observed that sometimes the salts which accelerate in one case may retard in another case. Hence, it will be interesting to study further this aspect as it may yield interesting results.

Effect of Ageing on the Activity of Cake Lipases

Finally it is thought that it will be better to study the effect of ageing on the activity of the cake lipase as in case this lipase is to be used on a large scale in industry, it must be very stable in its activity, at least for an appreciable amount of time. So the effect of ageing on groundnut cake lipase was studied.

Three samples of cake lipase were prepared by draining for 3 hours, one with low boiling petroleum ether, the other with acetone, the third with the mixture of acetone and low boiling petroleum ether (b. p. 56°) according to Longnecker's method (*loc. cit.*). All the three samples were completely dried, powdered and sieved through a 60 mesh sieve and used for the experiments. The hydrolysis of groundnut oil was carried out using each sample of the lipase at different period.

Each set of the experiments consisted of groundnut oil (1 c. c.), water (5 c. c.), acetate buffer (2 c. c.) of p_H 4.4 and 0.1 g. of lipase of each variety at different intervals of time, kept in the incubator at 37° for 2 hours and then the contents titrated against $N/10$ sodium hydroxide after the addition of 25 c. c. of neutral alcohol and warming for sometime. Always a blank accompanied the sample. The difference between the sample and the blank in terms of c. c. of $N/10$ -NaOH gives the activity of the lipase. The results are shown in Table XII.

TABLE XII

Difference in c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH between the sample and the blank for groundnut lipase dried in

Set No.	Time of ageing.	Petroleum ether.	Acetone.	Pet. ether-acetone mixture.
1	0 min.	2.5	1.1	1.8
2	40	3.3	1.4	1.9
3	24 hrs.	3.6	1.5	2.1
4	2 days	3.8	1.7	2.5
5	4	4.2	1.7	2.7
6	6	4.0	1.7	2.5
7	8	3.8	1.6	2.5
8	12	3.5	1.6	2.5
9	15	3.3	1.6	2.4
10	23	3.1	1.6	2.4
11	45	2.9	1.6	2.4
12	55	2.5	1.5	2.3
13	65	2.2	1.5	2.3
14	75	2.0	1.5	2.3
15	85	1.8	1.5	2.0
16	95	1.5	1.5	2.0
17	105	1.3	1.5	1.8
18	115	1.0	1.4	1.8
19	125	0.5	1.4	1.7

It is found that in all cases the activity increases up to 2 to 4 days and then decreases. The activity is greatest in the case of petroleum ether sample, slightly less in petroleum ether-acetone mixture dried sample, and the least in acetone-dried sample. But at the same time, the velocity of change in activity is less in case of acetone-dried sample, more in petroleum ether-acetone-dried mixture, and the most in petroleum ether dried sample. In other words, the greater the activity of the sample, the more rapid is the change of activity on ageing.

Of the three samples, acetone-dried sample is the best even though its activity is low, since it keeps its activity fairly constant for an appreciable time. But acetone and petroleum ether mixture dried sample can be used for short period experiments

since its activity is appreciably good and it also keeps its activity fairly constant for a short time.

From the above observations, it can be seen that in general, the cake lipases are less active since most of their activity might have been lost in the process of removing oil from seeds due to a large amount of heat and pressure. In case there is no other cheap source of lipase available, and if the urgent necessity arises, then the castor and groundnut cake lipases obtained by ghani method can be used for enzymic hydrolysis and the best substrate and buffer are groundnut oil and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer respectively.

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